

percentage (ESP) for the sodic soils was 7, 52, 69, and 80, respectively. Increasing salinity and sodicity levels reduced grain yield. By comparing reduction of yields at same Na⁺ contents in the shoot, we determined that salinity was more harmful than sodicity.

Analyses of mature rice shoots for Na⁺ and Cl⁻ content showed that plants grown in sodic conditions have relatively higher Na⁺ content at each sodicity level than at respective salinity conditions (Fig. 1).

Cl⁻ concentration was very high in shoots of plants grown in saline conditions (Fig. 2), and much higher at each salinity level than Na⁺. For example, at EC 15.9 dS/m, Cl⁻ was 2.5 times higher

2. Effect of salinity (a) and sodicity (b) on mature shoot Cl⁻ content of M1-48.

than Na⁺. Plants grown under sodic conditions had low Cl⁻ content, although there was a slight increase with an increase in sodicity stress. It is inferred that high

sensitivity of M1-48 to salinity is due to Cl⁻ metabolism rather than to that of Na⁺. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization DROUGHT TOLERANCE

VL Dhan 206, a new upland rice variety

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VL Dhan 206 is a 165- to 170-d variety released by the Uttar Pradesh State Varietal Release Committee in 1983 for upland areas. It is a pureline selection from local Bamni. VL Dhan 206 is

medium tall and medium tillering, with light green foliage and good panicle exertion. Panicles are semicompact with good spikelet fertility. Grains are medium-sized with light yellow husks and straw-colored apiculus. Kernels are white, translucent, and nonglutinous. The rice has medium amylose content and cooks dry. It is tolerant of blast and stem borer and has good seedling cold tolerance.

VL Dhan 206 yielded 24% more than check variety Majhera 3 in trials and 25%

Yield of VL Dhan 206 in multilocational trials, Almora, India.^a

Variety	Yield (t/ha)				
	1970-79 (17)	1980 (4)	1981 (6)	1982 (2)	Mean
VL Dhan 206	1.6	2.8	1.8	1.4	1.9
Majhera 3	1.2	2.5	1.4	1.2	1.5

^aNumber of trial sites is in parentheses.

more in farmer field demonstrations (see table). □

Pest Control and Management DISEASES

Saket-4 resistance to tungro virus (RTV)

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We evaluated Saket-4, IR8, and TN1 for RTV resistance. Varieties were planted together in 2.5 × 2-m plots in 4 replications in 1981 and 1982. Twenty-five plants in the center of each plot were

Table 1. The number of days needed for symptom development on rice plants inoculated with RTV at 30, 45 or 60 days after sowing (DAS), Bihar, India.

Symptom	Days needed for symptom development ^a					
	TN1			IR8		
	30 DAS	45 DAS	60 DAS	30 DAS	45 DAS	60 DAS
Interveinal chlorosis	7	7	12	7	7	12
Orange-yellow color	8	8	14	8	8	14
Yellowing	10	10	20	10	10	20
Leaf tilting	10	11	25	10	11	30
Leaf rolling	13	14	28	14	26	—
Incomplete leaf emergence	15	15	—	17	20	—
Delayed panicle initiation	8	6	4	6	4	2

^aNo symptoms developed in Saket-4.